

ASSESSMENT OF IN-VITRO CYTOTOXICITY ON BRINE SHRIMP LETHALITY TEST OF GREEN SEAWEED *CODIUM FLABELLATUM*

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Abstract

Background: Seaweeds, with their wide structural composition and extensive pharmacological activities, have gained recognition in the pharmaceutical industry for their potential health benefits and disease management properties. The purpose this study to investigate the cytotoxicity of three different extracts (ethanol, ethyl acetate, and n-Hexane) obtained from *Codium flabellatum*, a green algae species collected from the coastal areas of Karachi, Pakistan. Brine shrimp eggs were employed to evaluate the LC50 of *C. flabellatum* extracts. **Methods:** *Codium flabellatum* samples were collected from Karachi's coastal areas and subjected to extraction using solvents of various polarities (ethanol, ethyl acetate, and n-Hexane). Brine shrimp eggs were hatched and exposed to different concentrations (10-500 µg/ml) of each extract to determine the LC50 values. **Results:** The ethyl acetate extract showed the lowest cytotoxicity, with a mortality rate of 60% and an LC50 of 355.046. In contrast, ethanol and n-Hexane extracts displayed higher mortality rates of 95% and 90%, with corresponding LC50 values of 30.121 and 35.297, respectively. These findings indicate that the ethyl acetate extract is comparatively safer. **Conclusion:** The outcomes of the *Codium flabellatum* extracts' brine shrimp lethality test demonstrate the possible cytotoxicity of marine algae as well as the impact of extraction solvents on bioactivity. The ethyl acetate extract from *Codium flabellatum* shows lower cytotoxicity, indicating potential safety for pharmaceutical applications. Further research is essential to fully understand algae extract safety, establishing a foundation for future investigations into *Codium flabellatum*'s pharmacological potential in seaweed-based applications.

Keywords: *Codium Flabellatum*, Cytotoxicity, Green Seaweed, Marine Algae

INTRODUCTION

Seaweeds are commonly termed as macro algae with no true roots, leaves or stem. They are basically classified in four categories depends of their color some famous macro algae includes *Phaeophyceae* (brown algae), *Chlorophyta* (Green algae), *Chrysophyceae* (gold algae), *Rhodophyta* (red algae) [1].

Pakistan's coastal and inshore waters of the northern Arabian Sea have vibrant source of algal flora. Many seaweed and marine algae species have been shown to have varying levels of ascorbic acid in addition to carbohydrates, fats, minerals, and vitamins. Scientists are interested in using seaweed as a source of medicine because of the rising demand for medications manufactured from algae [2].

Macro algae are a significant food source, predominantly in Asian nations. Numerous studies exploring the phytochemicals of seaweeds with varied biological activity in pure or extracted forms have been published, revealing their potential to produce bioactive secondary metabolites. [3] Seaweeds contain a number of secondary metabolites, e.g., polysaccharides, agar, carrageenan, algin, mannitol, proteins, lipids, phenolic compounds, terpenes, fatty acids, sterols, etc. Because of these secondary metabolites, they are strongly pharmacologically active. It is reported that seaweeds have anticancer, anti-tumor, anti-viral, antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiproliferative, anti-angiogenesis, and anti-coagulant activity. [4, 5, 6]

Codium flabellatum is one of the green seaweeds belonging to the family Codiaceae and was identified by M. Nizamuddin in 2001 [7]. This family comprises two genera and six species. In our previous studies, we have reported different qualitative phytochemical compounds [8]. However, few pharmacological activities have been reported in the literature [9] and toxicity tests of this seaweed are still lacking. To address this gap, the brine shrimp lethality bioassay is employed as a valuable tool for detecting bioactive natural products [10]. This assay is a safe, rapid, inexpensive, reliable, and convenient method for conducting preliminary toxicity investigations of natural products. The objective of this study was to perform a brine shrimp lethality bioassay on three different extracts of *Codium flabellatum* to assess their cytotoxic potential.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Collection and authentication of seaweed:

Codium flabellatum (M. Nizamuddin) was obtained, identified, and authenticated with the voucher number (CYF-06) in collaboration with the Centre of Excellence in Marine Biology, University of Karachi, Pakistan. All seaweed was obtained from local beaches, including Kakapir, Sandspit, and Buleji in Karachi, Pakistan, at low tides.

Extraction:

Seaweed was dried and macerated with three solvents depending on their polarity (ethanol, ethyl acetate, and n-hexane). The macerate was processed through a rotary evaporator for the separation of solvents. Pure extracts were used for experimental purposes.

Hatching of *Artemia Salina*

For the hatching of *Artemia salina* cysts, 0.1 g of brine shrimp eggs (catalog no ASIN: B07JL8VMCB, from Vpoint Fish Food, and sourced from VPoint & Yiwu Jadear Trade) was added to autoclaved and cooled natural seawater, with constant aeration, in the dark, at a temperature of 25 °C. The cysts were hatched within 24 hours, and active nauplii of *A. salina* were selected for the toxicity test.

Brine Shrimp Lethality Test

This bioassay was conducted according to the Meyer *et.al.*, (1982) [11]. The stock solution was prepared by dissolving 20 mg of extracts in 2 mL of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), resulting in a DMSO concentration of 1%. The mixture was then subjected to sonication for 20 minutes. Test samples, namely ethanol, ethyl acetate, and n-hexane extracts of *C. flabellatum*, were serially diluted to achieve concentrations of 25, 50, 75, 100, and 500 µg/10 mL, respectively.

$$\% \text{ Mortality} = \frac{\text{Total number of dead nymph}}{\text{Total number of treated numph}} \times 100$$

In this case, if the death of the nymph occurred within the limit, then the data was justified by using Abbott's formula [12]. The LC₅₀ (lethal dose) and 95% confidence interval were determined through the Probit® analysis method using SPSS software.

Statistical Analysis

All the results were analyzed by standard deviation, ANOVA, Confidence Interval (CI), Tukey test.

RESULTS

A brine shrimp lethargy assay was performed to evaluate the in vitro cytotoxicity of green algae (*Codium flabellatum*). **Table 1** shows the results of six groups with a graded dose of 10, 25, 50, 75, 100, and 500 µg/ml, respectively. LC₅₀ was also identified with the confidence interval and other statistical tools (ANOVA, Tukey test, homogeneity of variances) from **Tables 2–5**. By comparing all three extracts of *C. flabellatum*, ethyl acetate was the safest among all, as it has a very low mortality rate. At the dose of 500 µg/ml, the rate of mortality was only 60%, with LC₅₀ = 355.046. By comparing it with ethanol and *n-hexane*, they have 95% and 90% of the mortality rate, with LC₅₀ = 30.121 and LC₅₀ = 25.297, respectively.

Table 1: Results for Brine Shrimp Lethargy Assay of *Codium flabellatum*

Extracts	10µg/ml	25µg/ml	50µg/ml	75µg/ml	100µg/ml	500µg/ml	LC ₅₀
Ethanol	25	43	58	73	85	95	30.121
Ethyl acetate	5	15	25	30	40	60	355.046
<i>n</i> -hexane	28	39	54	66	75	90	35.297

LC₅₀ > 1000 g/mL non-toxic, LC₅₀ <1,000 g/mL low toxic, LC₅₀ 100 - 500 g/mL medium toxic, LC₅₀ 0 - 100 g/mL highly toxic [18]

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics Table

Extracts	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Ethanol	6	63.1667	26.36981	10.76543	35.4933	90.8401	25.00	95.00
Ethyl acetate	6	29.1667	19.34339	7.89691	8.8670	49.4663	5.00	60.00
<i>n</i> -Hexane	6	58.6667	23.02752	9.40095	34.5008	82.8326	28.00	90.00
Total	18	50.3333	26.67010	6.28620	37.0706	63.5961	5.00	95.00

Table 3: Test of Homogeneity of Variances

Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
.534	2	15	.597

Table 4: ANOVA Table

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	4093.000	2	2046.500	3.838	.045
Within Groups	7999.000	15	533.267		
Total	12092.000	17			

Table 5: Multiple Comparisons Tukey Test

(I) Brand	(J) Brand	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Ethanol Extract	Ethyl Acetate Extract	34.00000	13.33250	.055	-.6308	68.6308
	<i>n</i> -Hexan Extract	4.50000	13.33250	.939	-30.1308	39.1308
Ethyl Acetate Extract	Ethanol Extract	-34.00000	13.33250	.055	-68.6308	.6308
	<i>n</i> -Hexan Extract	-29.50000	13.33250	.101	-64.1308	5.1308
<i>n</i> -Hexane Extract	Ethanol Extract	-4.50000	13.33250	.939	-39.1308	30.1308
	Ethyl Acetate Extract	29.50000	13.33250	.101	-5.1308	64.1308

DISCUSSION

Seaweeds, as rich sources of bioactive secondary metabolites with pharmacological applications.

From seaweeds, over 2400 marine-derived natural compounds have been identified; these compounds have been shown to have antitumor [15], antibacterial, antiviral, antineoplastic, and immune-stimulating properties [13, 14, 16]. In Asia, seaweeds have long been a part of traditional food and herbal medicines.

The brine shrimp lethality assay is an alternative bioassay method for determining the toxicity of marine natural products [17]. For this purpose, we employed the brine shrimp lethality test to identify toxic compounds in extracts, effectively assessing the cytotoxicity of three extracts through this economical and straightforward method. The results obtained from the brine shrimp lethality assay of *Codium flabellatum* extracts (ethanol, ethyl acetate, and n-hexane) are presented in Table 1. The assay was conducted at various concentrations (10 μ g/ml to 500 μ g/ml), and the lethality percentages were recorded after 24 hours. The LC₅₀ values, which show the concentration required to induce 50% death, were determined for each extract.

The toxicity index values (LC₅₀) reported by Clarkson et al. (2004) [18] are used to determine whether the extracts are toxic or non-toxic. According to this, extracts with LC₅₀ values above 1000 μ g/mL are non-toxic, and extracts with LC₅₀ values of 500–1000 μ g/mL are low-toxic. Our study found that, ethanol and n-hexane extracts exhibited increasing lethality with higher concentrations, reaching 95% and 90% mortality at 500 μ g/mL. The calculated LC₅₀ values for ethanol and n-hexane were 30.121 and 35.297, respectively, categorizing them as highly cytotoxic according to the classification criteria (LC₅₀ < 100 μ g/mL). Ethyl acetate extract displayed a concentration-dependent increase in lethality, with 60% mortality at 500 μ g/mL. In contrast to ethanol and n-hexane, its LC₅₀ >100 μ g/mL value was noticeably higher at 355.046, suggesting lower cytotoxicity. The highest lethality of the extracts of *C. flabellatum* was observed in this study, but the causes need to be further investigated.

Plant materials have cytotoxic effects because they include anticancer compounds [19], and many of the secondary metabolites produced by marine algae are well known for their cytotoxicity [20].

Ara et al. (1999) studied the cytotoxicity activity of *Artemia salina* in 22 ethanolic extracts of seaweed collected from Pakistan's Karachi coast. Only six extracts showed significant mortality. The LC₅₀ values for five brown macroalgae (*Stoechospermum marginatum*, *Sargassum swartzii*, *Stokeyia indica*, *Spatoglossum asperum* and *S. binderi*) and one green macroalga (*Caulerpa racemosa*) were 443, 507, 612, 928, 735, and 929 μ g mL⁻¹, respectively. Aqueous extracts of *S. indica* and *C. racemosa* had the highest efficacy (CL₅₀ < 70 μ g mL⁻¹). It was observed that the cytotoxicity may be caused by the polarity of various substances [19].

Another study by Ayesha *et al.* 2010 on seaweed growing near the Karachi coast found that eight species out of nine have cytotoxic effects against *Artemia salina*. The brine shrimp lethality test is reliable for studying bioactive compounds in seaweeds [21].

CONCLUSION

The brine shrimp lethality test results for *Codium flabellatum* extracts show the potential cytotoxicity of marine algae and the influence of extraction solvents on bioactivity. The findings contribute to the growing body of information about the pharmacological potential of marine organisms and lay the groundwork for further investigation of particular bioactive compounds identified in *Codium flabellatum* extract.

References

- 1) Makkar h p, Tran G, Heuzé v, Gigerreverdin S, Lessire M, Lebas F, and Ankers P (2016) Seaweeds for livestock diets: A review Animal Feed Science and Technology. 212: 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ANIFEEDSCI.2015.09.018>.
- 2) Najam R, Riaz B, Ali M S , Azhar I.(2015) Hematological Screening of Some Seaweed Found At Karachi Coast. International Journal of Healthcare Sciences 3: 2, 93-96.
- 3) Yasmeen. A. (2017) Phytochemical studies on major drifted seaweed species. PhD. thesis, Centre of Excellence in Marine Biology, University of Karachi, http://pr.hec.gov.pk/jspui/bitstream/123456789/125777/1/Afshan%20Yasmeen_Marine%20Bio_2018_UoK_PRR.pdf.
- 4) Shah, S.S, Huma, A., Baig,T, Rasheed, M., Ahmed, T., & Ibrahim, S. (2022) Preliminary Phycochemical and Physicochemical Evaluation of Red Seaweed *Coelarthrum Muelleri*. Journal of Hunan University Natural Sciences, 49(6).
- 5) Meinta, M D N, Harwanto, D, Choi, J.S (2022).A concise review of the bioactivity and pharmacological properties of the genus *Codium* (Bryopsidales, Chlorophyta).Journal of Applied Phycology.34,2827-2845.
- 6) Chakraborty, K., Lipton, A. P., Paulraj, R., & Chakraborty, R. D. (2010). Guaiane sesquiterpenes from seaweed *Ulva fasciata Delile* and their antibacterial properties. European journal of medicine chemistry, 45(6), 2237-2244.
- 7) Nizamuddin M. 2001.Genus *Codium* Stackhouse from northern coast of the Arabian Sea (Pakistan). Pakistan Journal of Marine Biology (Pakistan).
- 8) Ahmed, T., Huma, A., Rasheed, M., Baig, M.T, Rizvi, S.S, Gul, S., Ibrahim, S. (2022). Pharmacognostic Standardization and Phycochemical Evaluation of Green Seaweed *Codium Flabellatum*, Journal of Hunan University Natural Sciences. Vol 49, No 6.
- 9) Yasmeen, A. Ibrahim, M., Mohtasheem ul Hasan, M., Jilani, T, Shafique, S. and Rasheed, M., (2021). Phycochemical analyses and pharmacological activities of seven macroalgae of Arabian Sea, , Pak. J. Pharm. Sci., Vol.34, No.3, May, pp.963-969
- 10) Sarah, Q. S., Anny, F.C., and Misbahuddin, M. (2017) Brine shrimp lethality assay. Bangladesh J Pharmacol. 12: 186-18
- 11) B N Meyer , N R Ferrigni, J E Putnam, L B Jacobsen, D E Nichols, J L McLaughlin.1982.Brine shrimp: a convenient general bioassay for active plant constituents, Planta medica, 45(05), 31-34.

- 12) Abbott WS. 1925. A method of computing the effectiveness of an insecticide. *J. econ. Entomol.* Apr 1; 18(2):265-7.
- 13) Faulkner D.J. (2000). Marine natural products. *Nat. Prod. Rep.* ;17(1):7–55
- 14) Tziveleka L.A., Vagias C., Roussis V. (2003). Natural products with anti-HIV activity from marine organisms. *Curr. Top. Med. Chem.* 3(13):1512–1535.
- 15) Mayer A.M., Gustafson K.R. (2003). Marine pharmacology in 2000: antitumor and cytotoxic compounds. *Int. J. Canc.*; 105(3):291–299.
- 16) König G.M., Wright A.D. (1996). Marine natural products research: current directions and future potential. *Planta Med.*; 62(3):193–211.
- 17) Carballo J.L., Hernández-Inda Z.L., Pérez P., García-Grávalos M.D. (2002). A comparison between two brine shrimp assays to detect in vitro cytotoxicity in marine natural products. *BMC Biotechnol*;2(1):17
- 18) Clarkson, C., Maharaj, V.J., Crouch, N.R., Grace, O.M., Pillay, P., Matsabisa, M. G., Bhagwandin, N., Smith, P.J., Folb, P.I., (2004). In vitro antiplasmodial activity of medicinal plants native to ornaturalized in South Africa. *J Ethnopharm.* 92, 177-191.
- 19) Ara J., Sultana V., Ehteshamul.H. S, Qasim R. and Ahmed VU. (1999). Cytotoxic activity of marine macroalgae on *Artemia salina* (brine shrimp). *Phytother Res* 13: 304-307.
- 20) Harada H., Kamei Y. (1997). Selective cytotoxicity of marine algae extracts to several human leukemic cell lines. *Cytotechnology.* 25(1–3):213
- 21) Ayesha, H., V. Sultana, J. Ara, and S. Ehteshamul-Haque (2010). In vitro cytotoxicity of seaweeds from Karachi coast on brine shrimp. *Pakistan J. Bot.* 42(5): 3555-3560.